

EVALUATION OF PROGRESS OF PHYSICAL AGING ON VISCOELASTIC BEHAVIOR OF EPOXY RESIN

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1 Introduction

Mechanical behavior of thermosetting resins exhibit time and temperature dependence not only above the glass-transition temperature T_g but also below T_g . These resins generally do not exist in thermodynamic equilibrium state below T_g . The current state gradually moves towards the equilibrium state. The non-equilibrium state, however, is characterized by the transport mobility, which depends primarily on the degree of packing, or on the free volume. This state is approached asymptotically. As a result, the specific volume of resin decreases from B to B'' under the constant temperature as shown in Fig.1. Such a process is called physical aging and significantly affects mechanical behavior, especially the viscoelastic behavior of thermosetting resins. These examples have been shown by Struik [1], Kong [2], Sullivan [3], Sullivan et al [4], Hastie and Morris [5], Kasamori et al [6-7], Feldman and Gates [8].

Fig. 1. Specific volume versus temperature

We proposed the accelerated testing methodology to predict the long-term creep and fatigue strengths of

FRP based on the time-temperature superposition principle (TTSP) for the viscoelastic behavior of matrix resin and confirmed the applicability of this methodology for various kinds of FRP [9-10]. It is concluded from these results that the long-term viscoelastic behavior of matrix resin in the range of temperature below T_g should be accurately evaluated from the short-term measured data at elevated temperatures for the reliable prediction of the long-term strength of FRP.

In this paper, the experimental study has been carried out to clarify the influence of physical aging on the viscoelastic behavior of epoxy resins. We first construct the master curves of storage modulus at the reference temperature for epoxy resins aged at various aging conditions. We then select a reference aging condition corresponding to specific aging temperature T_{a0} and aging time t_{a0} . Master curves for various aging conditions were found, after suitable horizontal and vertically shifts, to collapse into a single smooth curve corresponding to the master curve for the reference. The single smooth curve thus obtained is designated as the grand master curve. In this process, we introduce the aging progressive rate similar to the time-temperature shift factor used in the construction of the master curves.

2 Influence of Physical Aging on Viscoelastic Behavior

The viscoelastic behavior, e.g. storage modulus versus time curves under temperatures below and above T_g are respectively shown by black and red solid curves, while those for different physical aging progress under temperature below T_g are shown by solid and dotted black curves in Fig.2. If the same

TTSP holds for the viscoelastic behavior under the wide range of temperature from below T_g to above T_g , regardless the progress of physical aging, these curves can be superimposed each other, and then the grand master curve can be constructed. Therefore, it can be presumed that the change of storage modulus with temperature and progress of physical aging is characterized by the shifting of these curves. From the next section, we conducted experimental verification for this assumption.

Fig.2. Influence of physical aging on the viscoelastic behavior

3 Experimental Procedures

The composition of resin used in this study is deglycidyl ether of bis-phenol A (jER 828) for epoxy resin, methyl nadic anhydride for hardener, and 2-ethyl-4-methyl-imidazole as shown in Table I. Epoxy resin was cured at 70°C for 12 hours, and then post-cured at 150°C for 4 hours and at 190°C for 2 hours followed by a slow cooling at 0.5°C per minute.

Table I Composition and cure schedule of epoxy resin

Composition		
Epoxy	: jER828	100
Hardener	: MHAC-P	103.6
Cure accelerator	: 2-Ethyl-4-methylimidazole	1
Cure schedule		
70°C × 12hr + 150°C × 4hr + 190°C × 2hr + (-0.5°C/min)		

Epoxy resin cured as mentioned above was heat-treated at fifteen different conditions which are combined three levels of aging temperature $T_a = 80^\circ\text{C}$, 100°C , 120°C and five levels of aging time $t_a = 10^3 \text{ min}$, $3 \times 10^3 \text{ min}$, 10^4 min , $3 \times 10^4 \text{ min}$, 10^5 min as shown in Table II. The viscoelastic behavior for aged epoxy resin was measured by dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) under various frequencies and temperatures under three-point bending (shown in Fig.3) with 0.1% of constant strain amplitude. In addition, the density of epoxy resin was measured by the density gradient column using calcium nitrate solution.

Table II Aging condition

Aging temperature T_a [°C]	80, 100, 120
Aging time t_a [min]	10^3 , 3×10^3 , 10^4 , 3×10^4 , 10^5

Fig.3. Three-point bending for DMA

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Master curve of storage modulus

The left side of Fig.4(a) shows the storage modulus E' versus time t (inverse of frequency f) at various temperatures T of epoxy resin aged at $T_a = 120^\circ\text{C}$ for $t_a = 10^3 \text{ min}$ as an example. The master curve of E' versus reduced time t' was constructed by shifting E' at various constant temperatures along the log scale of t and log scale of E' as shown in the right side of Fig.4(a). Figure 4(b) and 4(c) respectively show the time-temperature shift factor a_{T_0} and the temperature shift factor b_{T_0} which are obtained by constructing the master curve of E' of epoxy resin aged at $T_a = 120^\circ\text{C}$ for several aging times.

(a) Master curve of storage modulus for epoxy resin aged at $T_a=120^\circ\text{C}$ for $t_a=10^3\text{min}$

(b) Time-temperature shift factor for epoxy resin aged at $T_a=120^\circ\text{C}$ for several aging times

(c) Temperature shift factor for epoxy resin aged at $T_a=120^\circ\text{C}$ for several aging times

Fig.4. Master curve and shift factors of storage modulus for epoxy resin

4.2 Grand master curve of storage modulus

The master curves of E' for epoxy resins aged at fifteen aging conditions were constructed as shown in the left side of Fig.5. The right side of Fig.5 shows the grand master curve of E' at a reference aging condition $t_{a0}=10^3\text{min}$ and $T_{a0}=80^\circ\text{C}$ obtained by shifting master curves of E' horizontally and vertically for various aging conditions.

The aging progressive rates β and γ which are horizontal and vertical shift factors for constructing the grand master curve defined by

$$\beta = \frac{t'}{t''}, \gamma = \frac{E'(t', T_a)}{E'(t'', T_{a0})} \quad (1)$$

The β and γ versus aging time t_a at various aging temperatures T_a are shown on the left side of Figs.6(a) and 6(b). Master curves of β and γ are constructed by shifting β and γ at various aging temperatures along the log scale of aging time until they overlap each other as shown in the right side of Figs.6(a) and 6(b). The density ρ versus aging time t_a at various aging temperatures T_a are shown in the left side of Fig.6(c). Master curve of ρ is constructed by shifting ρ at various aging temperatures along the log scale of aging time until they overlap each other as shown in the right side of Fig.6(c). Figure 7 shows the time-temperature shift factors for constructing the master curves of β , γ and ρ . These time-temperature shift factors agree well with each other.

Figure 8 shows the relationship between β , γ and ρ for fifteen aging conditions. These figures show the aging progressive rate and the density satisfy the one-to-one correspondence regardless the aging time and aging temperature.

We checked chemical change of epoxy resin after heat treatment for several aging conditions by DSC. Figure 9 shows the DSC curves of epoxy resin aged at $T_a=80^\circ\text{C}$ for $t_a=10^3\text{min}$ and at $T_a=120^\circ\text{C}$ for $t_a=10^5\text{min}$. Both curves are clearly different with each other. Therefore, it is considered that the chemical change occurs for epoxy resin aged at $T_a=120^\circ\text{C}$ for $t_a=10^5\text{min}$ during heat treatment.

Figure 10(a) shows the relationship between time-temperature shift factor a_{T0} plus aging progressive rate β and density, while Fig.10(b) shows the relationship between temperature shift factor b_{T0}

plus aging progressive rate γ and density. The plots for epoxy resin aged at $T_a=100^\circ\text{C}$ for $t_a=10^5\text{min}$, $T_a=120^\circ\text{C}$ for $t_a=3 \times 10^4\text{min}$ and 10^5min are indicated by light symbols because it is considered that the

chemical change occurred for these conditions. It is respectively shown in these figures that there are one-to-one correspondence between these shift factors and polymer density.

Fig.5. Grand master curves of storage modulus for epoxy resin

(a) Aging progressive rate β

(b) Aging progressive rate γ

(c) Density ρ

Fig.6. Master curves of aging progressive rates and density

Fig.7. Time-temperature shift factors for aging progressive rates and density

(a) Aging progressive rate β

(b) Aging progressive rate γ

Fig.8. Relationship between aging progressive rates and density

Fig.9 DSC curves for epoxy resin aged at $t_a=10^3$ min and $T_a=80^\circ\text{C}$, $t_a=10^5$ min and $T_a=120^\circ\text{C}$

(a) Time-temperature shift factor

(b) Temperature shift factor

Fig.10 Relationship between shift factor and density

5 Conclusion

The master curves of storage modulus of epoxy resin for various aging conditions were found to collapse into a single smooth curve corresponding to a reference aging condition after suitable horizontal and vertical translations. The aging progressive rate which are the amount of horizontal and vertical translations can be used to estimate the aging process. We have also shown that there is one-to-one correspondence between the time-temperature shift factor and polymer density.

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